

შოთა რუსთაველის საერთაშორისო
ეროვნული სამეცნიერო ფონდი

SHOTA RUSTAVELI NATIONAL SCIENCE
FOUNDATION OF GEORGIA

*We seek to provide Gender Equality **inside our organisation** and implement **structural changes** to **increase** the female researchers in **STEM** fields, **improve** their **career prospects** and integrate a **gender dimension in research and innovation**.*

Gender Equality Status Analysis

An extensive assessment of **gender bias** and **inequalities** both inside the Institution and in the external Innovation Ecosystem where it is positioned.

This research has been carried out by SRNSFG in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The internal assessment followed the **three ERA priorities on Gender Equality*** and examined them in the context of **specific activity/service areas** inside SRNSFG through the collection of qualitative and quantitative data.

The data collection was conducted by the institution researchers, through **desk research, policy analysis, interviews, surveys and focus groups.**

Key Findings

HUMAN RESOURCES

There are **no** particular **gender-sensitive recruitment protocols/policies** in place inside SRNSFG, although the Organisation is obliged to follow the national regulations.

In recruitment processes, more females apply for open positions across all departments, succeed and have temporary contracts. However, they get a **middle or low management position**, while top management positions are covered by males.

*Council of the European Union (2015). [Conclusions on advancing Gender Equality in the European Research Area](#). RECH 295, COMPET 551, SOC 703

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The Organisation **hasn't adopted any transparent and flexible promotion/tenure criteria for the promotion of staff yet**, e.g. continuing education as well as individual performance measurement, neither for measures to support employees during major life events like childbirth, care work etc. This seems to refer to **work-life balance issues** in the Organisation, and the highest share of females dropping out in recent years might signal this.

INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE

Currently, there are **no strategies and/or policies** to foster gender balance in decision-making process inside SRNSFG.

No gender-sensitive budgeting is applied and **no mentoring or coaching** services/activities for leadership positions dedicated to women are in place.

The **gendered composition** of governing administration boards, committees and/or ad hoc strategic working groups is **significantly imbalanced**, due to a notable majority of male members.

82% Male Members

18% Female Members

Despite there is **no specific action plan about formal communications**, SRNSFG uses **inclusive language** while the content is **free of sexist language** and discriminatory terminology.

In terms of internal communication, the staff adopts **institutional guidelines and local laws** on the use of gender-sensitive language but **relevant training is not taking place** and there are **no further guidelines** on gender-sensitive non-biased communication/language use.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

RESEARCH FUNDING

There is **no data available on the gender ratio in the composition** of funding decision making bodies. The Organisation's policies about the recruitment of evaluators **do not include any specific gender-sensitive protocols.**

Share of women and men in scientific evaluation/selection panels/committees in the last 3 years

The Organisation recruits research evaluators based on an **official Code of Conduct**, but it **does not include any gender sensitive criteria** and currently they are mostly men. They do not receive any additional training or guidelines on gender stereotypes and unconscious bias.

Moreover, the **integration of the gender dimension** into research content is **not yet foreseen** by SRNSFG as a requirement in calls for research funding, since there are not in place guidelines or training for grant applicants and evaluators for this topic.

INTERSECTIONALITY

At the moment, the only available document that includes the idea of gender equality in conjunction with other discriminations and structural inequalities is the Decree **N187, Article 14 of SRNSFG Director General**. There are **no other specific institutional measures** concerning this issue, which implies the need for awareness raising actions on this topic.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

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Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

The first part of the external assessment included an analysis of the **national legal and policy framework**. The second is, focused on the **National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems**. A **context analysis** was implemented through a dedicated desk research and complemented with interviews with internal stakeholders. In addition to the context analysis, a **mapping** was conducted by SRNSFG to identify existing and potential synergies with external stakeholders. The mapping comprised a focus group with internal stakeholders, a survey for external stakeholders and a Social Network Analysis.

Key Findings

NATIONAL LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK

At present, three key national agencies are responsible for the advancement of gender equality in the country:

The Gender Equality Council of the Parliament,
The Gender Department of the Public Defender's Office
The Inter-Agency Commission on Gender Equality, Violence against Women and Domestic Violence Issues

The most relevant piece of legislation is the **Law of Georgia on Gender Equality**, which determines the state's obligation to ensure equality of women and men in all spheres of public life, including education and science.

However, both the national legislation and national action plans on gender equality **do not contain any specific mechanisms** to promote the underrepresented gender in **higher education or scientific research and innovation**; and the integration of **gender dimension** in research is **not addressed** by any program.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

Overall, the ratio of female students and researchers studying and/or making research in STEM disciplines is **about half** of the equivalent of males.

STEM Students

Researchers in Engineering & Tech

In addition, there are **less women founders of start-ups** than their male counterparts; while the discrepancy is even more notable in the share of **company owners** where **the majority ownership is male dominated**.

Founders of start-ups by gender

Majority ownership of companies by gender

National support schemes for the development of technical and business services are in place to assist enterprises to introduce innovative activities in their production processes. However, **the integration of the gender dimension in such processes is not addressed**.

Female entrepreneurship is supported through strategies stressing the importance for deeper involvement of women in entrepreneurial and economic activities. Despite the supportive framework, gender stereotypes persist, leading to a **gender-based division of work and gaps in economic opportunities**.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

The Social Network Analysis included 40 external stakeholders, the majority of them belonging to the Academia & Universities sector. Overall, **24 collaborations are led by women in SRNSFG** and consist mainly of joint calls and projects, multiple workshops, webinars and joint events, **but no collaborations are in place with specific reference to gender equality.**

Some of the involved stakeholders stated that they have already implemented **actions in order to overcome gender inequalities**, but there is a shared willingness for further collaboration with SRNSFG with specific reference to gender equality in order to overcome persistent imbalances.

Actions such as the **co-organisation of initiatives** (i.e., discussions, events, open lectures, seminars etc.), submission of **research projects**, sharing **good experiences** in academic and scientific environments and the adoption of **dedicated grants for female researchers** have been proposed

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

This research has been conducted in the context of Horizon 2020 project, **CALIPER**.

The results will be used for the project's next implementation phases.

SRNSFG is one of the 9 Research Organisations across Europe which participates in CALIPER to develop a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** and engage the local Innovation Hubs to transfer the gained knowledge beyond academia.

Discover more about CALIPER

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